

Technology and Well-being from the Perspectives of Older Persons: A Scoping Review

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Abstract

Objective: The objective of this scoping review is to identify the benefits and challenges of technologies on well-being from the perspective of older persons.

Introduction: Population ageing is defining the world demographic landscape. Years 2021 and 2020 were recognized as the Decade of Healthy Aging which determined the need to support well-being among older persons. Technologies have proven to provide positive psychological well-being that improve wellness and resilience in this population.

Inclusion criteria: Studies involved health participants aged ≥ 60 years; technologies to improve physical or mental well-being of older persons; technologies used at home, care retirements homes or long-term care environments; and publications in English and Spanish. Studies that focused on implanted or outdoor technologies, as well as technologies for any rehabilitation purposes or related to telehealth/e-health/remote monitoring/telemedicine; participants with any mental health illness/condition/rehabilitation process; or participants who required specific medications or nutrition treatments provided using technologies were excluded.

Methods: The search was conducted during 2022 in Scopus, PubMed, SpringerLink, and Academic Search. Thematic analysis was used to identify patterns within the data, code, and categorise information for further analysis. A Technology Readiness Level (TRL) scale was used to analyse each technology maturity level. After data collection was completed on an Excel™ spreadsheet, all data was color-coded to identify main results. Wilcock's perspective on well-being was the framework for understanding the construct and analysing benefits and challenges with technologies.

Conclusion: The objective of this scoping review is to assess how the use or implementation of technologies related to the perception of well-being from the standpoint of the older population who require environmental adaptations for enhancing occupational engagement and participation.

Introduction

Currently, ageing is considered a relevant topic due to the various transitions that the person must face related to personal, physical, mental, and social aspects such as a growing risk of disease, occupational transitions (e.g., retirement), relocation to housing options or family environments, and often loss of independence (World Health Organization, 2022).

According to the WHO (2022), supportive environments promote good health and the enablement of valued occupations; homes, neighbourhoods, and communities have a direct effect on how people age. Consequently, it is critical that social and environmental adaptations contemplate the needs of aged population. Schorderet et al., (2022) described various dimensions regarding adaptations such as safety, ease to use, independence, comfort, and preventive measures, which if implemented in community and household settings, can positively impact performance on daily activities, safety, autonomy, function and independence (Szanton et al., 2011). Furthermore, the relationship between older persons and the environment are complex. Environments are intrinsically linked to occupational participation in meaningful activities. Therefore, health decline emerges when participation barriers exit and when there is a lack of occupational engagement (Gaye Peyton et al., 2019).

As the world's older population grows and life expectancy increases, monitoring and health management has become increasingly important. Digital technologies, as tools to access health status in different environments, and opportunities for quality remote care have been described (Chen et al., 2023). Additionally, technologies based on positive psychological well-being that improve wellness and resilience have also been explored (Grossi et al., 2020).

Scientific literature presents a broad range of publications that address the use of technologies for aging population, with a predominantly rehabilitation approach and functional improvements (Hassett et al., 2020; Snoek et al., 2021). Nevertheless, to the best of our knowledge, perception of the older persons towards the use of technologies have not been reported in integrative studies. Moreover, qualitative methodological approaches related to the impact that these experiences may have on well-being has not been implemented. We seek to adopt a person-centred approach aiming at recognizing and promoting active participation of the older population on decision making and well-being with the use of technologies (Jobe, 2022).

Review question

Since the aim of this study, it to identify and map the technologies that are used to enhance well-being in older personas as well as their benefits and challenges that influence mental and physical dimensions, two specific research questions are proposed for this scoping review: 1) What is known from the existing literature about technologies designed for older persons use? and 2) What kind of benefits and challenges do the use of these technologies report in regard of well-being?

Keywords

Aged population; interprofessional; occupational engagement; technology; well-being.

Eligibility criteria

Participants

Healthy participants aged ≥ 60 years. Participants in the studies must be the main user and source of an opinion, perspective, or provide information with the use of an assessment tool (i.e., quantitative survey, standardized or non-standardized instrument, qualitative evaluation or observation) about the technology that was used. Opinions must encompass any aspect related to physical and mental well-being. Participants who required specific medications or nutrition treatments provided using technologies will be excluded.

Concept

Technologies (hardware/software/mixed) to improve the physical or mental well-being of older persons. Exclusion criteria related to the concept of technology are outdoor technologies; technologies for any rehabilitation purposes; technologies related to telehealth/e-health/remote monitoring/telemedicine; or if the main goal is related to treatment of any mental health condition/rehabilitation process.

Context

The context of technology use will be home, care retirements homes or long-term care environments where older persons live and have the opportunity to interact with the technology.

Types of Sources

This scoping review will consider both experimental and quasi-experimental study designs including. In addition, analytical observational studies including prospective and retrospective cohort studies, case-control studies and analytical cross-sectional studies will be considered for inclusion. This review will also consider descriptive observational study designs including case series, individual case reports and descriptive cross-sectional studies for inclusion. Any type of literature review (e.g., systematic reviews, rapid reviews, scoping reviews, etc.) will be excluded.

Qualitative studies will also be considered that focus on qualitative data related to perception of older persons about the use and experience with technologies that are intended to provide physical or mental well-being.

Methods

The proposed scoping review will be conducted in accordance with the The Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) methodology for scoping reviews (Aromataris & Munn, 2020) and the Practical Guide proposed by Pollock et al., (2021).

Search strategy

The search strategy will aim to locate both published and unpublished studies. An initial limited search in Scopus was undertaken to identify articles on the topic. The text words contained in the titles abstract, and key words of relevant articles were used to develop a full search strategy in PubMed, Springer link, and ProQuest. (see Appendix I). The search strategy, including all identified keywords and index terms, will be adapted for each included database and/or information source.

Studies published in any English and Spanish will be included. Studies published since 2015 to 2022 will be included.

Sources of unpublished studies/ grey literature to be searched include Google Scholar and Publish or Perish.

Study/Source of Evidence selection

Following the search, all identified citations will be collated and uploaded into Zotero (Zotero, 2023) and duplicates removed. Following a pilot test, titles and abstracts will then be screened by two or more independent reviewers for assessment against the inclusion criteria for the review. Potentially relevant sources will be retrieved in full. The full text of selected citations will be assessed in detail against the inclusion criteria by two or more independent reviewers. Reasons for exclusion of sources of evidence at full text that do not meet the inclusion criteria will be recorded and reported in the scoping review. Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers at each stage of the selection process will be resolved through discussion, or with an additional reviewer/s. The results of the search and the study inclusion process will be reported in full in the final scoping review and presented in a Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses extension for scoping review (PRISMA-ScR) flow diagram (Tricco et al., 2018).

Data Extraction

Data will be extracted from papers included in the scoping review by two or more independent reviewers using a data extraction tool developed by the reviewers in Excel™. The data extracted will include specific details about the participants, concept, context, study methods and key findings relevant to the review question/s.

All data will be color-coded to identify main results. Colour-codification will encompass aspects related to object, function, benefits and challenges, and Technology Readiness Level (TRL). After analysing results, thematic areas and emerging subthemes will be analysed, discussed, and unified.

A draft extraction form is provided (see Appendix II). The draft data extraction tool will be modified and revised as necessary during the process of extracting data from each included

evidence source. Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers will be resolved through discussion, or with an additional reviewer/s. If appropriate, authors of papers will be contacted to request missing or additional data, where required.

Data Analysis and Presentation

Data will be presented graphically, and a narrative summary will accompany results.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Universidad del Rosario and Pontificia Universidad Javeriana for promoting interprofessional and interinstitutional research opportunities.

Professor Daniel Alejandro Quiroga participated in the conception of the idea and as a reviewer in earlier stages of the research.

Students Manuela Loaiza, Laura Camila Acosta, and Paola Camila Castro participated as initial reviewers and helped with the calibration process, identification and screening of articles that resulted from the first search.

This scoping review research contributed towards the bachelor's degree in biomedical engineering of Paula Andrea Acosta (PAA).

Funding

This research was not financed.

Conflicts of interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to disclose

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Appendices

Appendix I: Search strategy

("technology" OR "monitoring" OR "smart" OR "care" OR "wellness" OR "support") AND ("home" OR "geriatrics" OR "retirement home" OR "retirement community") AND ("older people" OR "elderly" OR "adults").

Appendix II: Data extraction instrument

Title
Author(s) and year of publication
Country
Institution/University
Study/technology goal
Study design
Elder participants
Type of Technology (hardware/software /mixed/mobile APP)
Name of the technology
Availability in the market (yes or no)
Cost if any
How the technology was used task/procedure/protocol
TRL scale (1 to 9) whole solution
Instrument or approach for collecting data (Interview, focus group, survey...)
Outcomes (benefits)
Outcomes (difficulties)
Conclusions/Observations/Other findings
Reported limitations